

Pedagogical experiences on the didactic transposition of knowledge and research skills in teachers

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Abstract—

Their objective was to understand the pedagogical experiences of university teachers on the didactic transposition of knowledge and research skills in a Peruvian university during the year 2025. The research followed a qualitative approach and employed an Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) design proposed by Jonathan Smith, which enabled an in-depth examination of participants' lived experiences and the meanings they assigned to the phenomenon. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with five university professors, and the findings were organized into four subcategories: contextualized knowledge, pedagogical accompaniment and adaptation, deep understanding, and ethical commitment to critical formation. Results indicate that didactic transposition is conceived as an ethical and contextualized process that re-signifies disciplinary knowledge; however, traditional methodologies persist, limiting the development of investigative competencies. It is concluded that universities should strengthen planned pedagogical mediation strategies to promote a critical approach to didactic transposition and the integral development of investigative skills.

Keywords: didactic transposition; pedagogical experience; investigative skills; higher education; teacher training.

I. INTRODUCTION

Achieving an increase in research capacity represents a major challenge for higher education, since this process generates the ability to adequately face the challenges of today's world. Therefore, for teachers it is critical in their practice, beyond merely supporting the subject matter, to implement pedagogical strategies that transform scientific knowledge into material that can be assimilated and conveyed to students (Gavancho, 2023). On the other hand, it should be noted that there are certain university contexts that restrict the implementation of research practice, leaving it confined to theoretical guidelines that have no connection whatsoever with real research practice. In this new educational scenario, the teacher becomes a mediator of knowledge, generating interesting and relevant learning experiences (UNESCO, 2022). The relationship between pedagogical methods and the practice of research skills is important for the training of critical and innovative professionals who are prepared to discuss knowledge in real and complex contexts.

Within the international context, the need for transformation becomes even more urgent, as most university lecturers still face difficulties in translating specialized scientific knowledge into pedagogical language that is accessible and meaningful for their students, which highlights the urgency of strengthening these skills in teacher training programs (Rivera de Parada & Mainegra, 2023). Likewise, it has been emphasized that, despite institutions increasingly demanding greater academic output, not all faculty members have solid research training or an institutional environment that helps them continuously improve these skills (Rivera-Herrera, 2024). In line with this, UNESCO (2022) reported that 62% of university lecturers in Latin America have not received formal pedagogical training, which has limited their ability to mediate between disciplinary knowledge and effective teaching. Similarly, the World Bank (2019) pointed out that more than 60% of lecturers in middle-income countries lacked specific didactic preparation,

representing a significant barrier to research-based educational innovation. Likewise, according to the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2021), only 45% of university lecturers in member countries felt prepared to foster research skills, while 35% showed a general lack of knowledge about research in the academic field and also stated that they did not have institutional incentives to develop research activities.

In addition, it has been observed that a certain number of university lecturers have encountered difficulties in articulating research processes with teaching practices, which has prevented them from fully developing their role in training students in a comprehensive, critical, and contextualized manner. This gap between teaching and research represents a challenge to strengthening the consolidation of an academic culture focused on fostering reflection, innovation, and the construction of knowledge within the educational community. Added to this problem is the predominance of traditional methodologies, based on lecture-centered classes and the theoretical transmission of knowledge, which have proven to be an obstacle to effective learning of research. Such methodologies have not facilitated the practical application of research knowledge, thereby limiting the development of the critical and practical skills students need to actively engage in the research process, reducing opportunities to participate in effective research activities that are essential for their training in this field.

From this perspective, research was connected to the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), specifically SDG 4 on quality education through education that is adapted to the context and the learner. In addition, it encouraged the professional growth of teachers, stimulated innovation and academic inquiry, and simplified the adaptation of curricula to different scenarios, thus contributing to inclusive instruction.

Considering the problems identified in the university context, particularly those related to limitations in the pedagogical mediation of research, the following question was formulated as the general research problem: What are the pedagogical experiences regarding the didactic transposition of research knowledge and skills among teachers at a Peruvian university during the year 2025?

On the other hand, in order to support the relevance and robustness of the study, a comprehensive rationale was presented that articulates its justifications. From a theoretical standpoint, the study was justified by the existence of limited academic production that addresses in an integrated manner the didactic transposition of knowledge and the development of research skills in the university context, with the aim of generating new theoretical references that expand the field of study, consolidate these categories as valid objects of analysis, and serve as a solid foundation for future inquiries in the field of higher education didactics and research training.

At the epistemological level, the study was grounded in the interpretive–constructivist paradigm, which conceives knowledge as a dynamic, contextual construction mediated by the interaction between subject and environment. This perspective made it possible to achieve a solid understanding of teachers' experiences regarding didactic transposition and research skills, providing methodological coherence to the study and strengthening the field through contextualized approaches (Lincoln & Guba, 1985).

From a practical perspective, its implementation was essential because it addresses a specific need of universities: to overcome the disconnect between disciplinary knowledge and teaching practice, in order to strengthen teaching practices through more effective and contextualized mediation strategies that promote both the meaningful appropriation of knowledge and the development of research competencies in students.

From a methodological perspective, a qualitative approach was established with an Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) design, as it essentially seeks to understand the experiences and meanings that participants attribute to the phenomenon under study. This methodological choice provides access to a subjective and situated reality. The semi-structured interview was selected because it offered the possibility of open and in-depth dialogue in accordance with the objectives of the study. The methodology was adopted to access interpretative and meaningful knowledge, thereby contributing to a comprehensive and human-centered understanding of the educational phenomenon.

This study explored the experiences of university teachers regarding the didactic transposition of research knowledge and skills, focusing on how they contextualize, mediate, and assess knowledge in their teaching. The general objective of this study was to understand the pedagogical experiences related to the didactic transposition of research knowledge and skills among teachers at a Peruvian university in 2025.

The theoretical foundations constituted the conceptual support that underpinned the research, providing a frame of reference that guided analysis and interpretation. In the context of this study, a main holistic category was considered: the pedagogical experience lived by teachers regarding the didactic transposition of research knowledge and skills. Pedagogical experience is defined as an active and reflective process that combines teaching practice with the construction of knowledge. This helps teachers examine their experiences, identify aspects that can be improved, and strengthen skills that are important for their professional growth (Cuéllar et al., 2022).

Furthermore, it is understood as a cultural and educational phenomenon, constituted by a network of meanings that directly influences the training processes constructed by teachers. These meanings, when lived and appropriated by students, become a means that allows them to identify their own formative intentions. Through them, students recognize topics that awaken their research interest, mobilize their curiosity, and strengthen their desire to know (Vargas, 2015).

Didactic transposition is the process of transforming knowledge produced within science or academia (scholarly knowledge) into knowledge to be taught (according to didactic criteria) and into knowledge taught when it reaches the classroom (Chevallard, 1985). It is the method used to transform the scientific and academic knowledge intended to be taught in schools. This knowledge must be adapted to teaching conditions, which implies a change in its original structure from the moment it becomes accessible to students (Ramos, 2013). It is a process of recontextualization of knowledge—that is, a transformation of knowledge based on the demands of the educational system. This perspective provides a critical view of how original content can be transformed, becoming something different with complex and rich content, which will be questioned in terms of the quality of learning (Joshua & Dupin, 1993).

On the other hand, research skills are understood as the mastery of psychological and practical actions that rationally regulate research activity, putting into action the individual's knowledge and habits, while enabling the identification and resolution of problems through scientific research (Pérez & López, 1999). They constitute a set of capacities of diverse nature that begin to develop even before individuals engage in systematic research training processes; that is, they are generated prior to formal access to research training, as they are necessary to conduct high-quality research (Martínez & Márquez, 2015). They involve the mastery of actions developed to solve tasks in educational, professional, and research situations, using scientific methodological resources (Machado et al., 2008). Research skills are a manifestation of the content of teaching, in which there is mastery of practical or evaluative actions that allow the rational regulation of activity and are grounded in the knowledge possessed by the individual to face situations and solve concrete problems through scientific research (López, 2001).

Along these lines, within the research framework, four subcategories were considered. The first was the teacher's pedagogical experience in didactic transposition and contextualized knowledge, which reveals the teacher's ability to transform disciplinary knowledge into teachable knowledge by attending to the students' reality and context. To this end, the selection and organization of content take on particular importance, as they involve arranging the most relevant knowledge in a progressive and coherent manner in relation to pedagogical purposes (Zabalza, 2007). At the same time, information gathering is articulated as a competence that enables teachers to identify research problems, define hypotheses, and obtain data from credible sources, thereby strengthening the construction of contextual and reflective knowledge (Casanova et al., 2020). In any case, this subcategory indicates that didactic transposition is not merely content adaptation, but is understood as a process of critical interpretation and pedagogical contextualization grounded in teaching experience.

The second subcategory corresponded to the teacher's pedagogical experience as guidance and adaptation to the student's pace of learning, where pedagogical mediation is understood as the process through which the teacher acts as a mediator or facilitator of learning, using strategies and didactic resources aimed at the active construction of knowledge. This idea aligns with the formulation of Díaz (2005) and with Vygotsky (1978), who emphasize the intervention of the mediator in the student's cognitive and social development. This formulation leads to the understanding that research planning and implementation become a form of mediation, as they involve precisely defining objectives, approaches, and appropriate analytical techniques to give meaning to a teaching–learning process with contextualized and reflective practices (Casanova et al., 2020). Thus, pedagogical experience and teaching mediation emerge as strengths that articulate educational practice with formative research.

The third subcategory focused on the teacher's pedagogical experience in fostering deep understanding and the student's critical transformation. In this regard, learning assessment is constructed through an ongoing and comprehensive process based on verifying the extent to which students have appropriated and mobilized knowledge, thus constituting an evaluation that inherently incorporates a formative and reflective approach. As Perrenoud (1993) states, assessment must continuously provide feedback to the educational process in order to promote autonomy and continuous improvement. The communication of results is likewise an important phase of teaching–research practice, as it conveys findings in a precise and rigorous manner through academic dissemination and, in doing so, contributes to the formation of other scholars (Casanova et al., 2020). Pedagogical experience is therefore understood as a transformative process that links the construction of understanding with concrete and critical action and with the broad dissemination of knowledge.

Finally, the fourth was an emergent subcategory, referring to the teacher's pedagogical experience regarding ethical commitment to critical education and knowledge oversight. This can be understood as a comprehensive process through which the teacher performs an ethical and transformative role in university teaching. In didactic transposition, the teacher does not limit their role to content adaptation, but rather engages in critical mediation aimed at contextualizing knowledge according to students' needs. Thus, pedagogical practice assumes a space for ethical reflection, in which knowledge acquires social and emancipatory value (Ibrahim et al., 2018). Furthermore, knowledge oversight refers to the teacher's ability to ensure that students do not merely memorize, but also understand, analyze, and apply knowledge to reality. This ethical practice has a clear impact on the quality of learning and on the education of university students; as argued by Mahmood et al. (2024), who establish a relationship between teachers' ethical standards and students' academic performance. Ethical commitment in university teaching goes beyond the mere transmission of content, as it promotes in students the construction of a professional "ethical compass,"

encouraging critical reflection that can lead them to act socially in response to the context they face (Gottardello & Pàmies, 2019). At the same time, ethics in teaching also implies a constant process of reflection, a conscientious concern for the consequences of learning, and responsibility for sensitivity to the sociocultural conditions in which students emerge, as noted by Yildiz (2022). In this way, the pedagogical experience of the university teacher is reaffirmed as an ethical and pedagogical action that articulates knowledge, critique, and social commitment.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. *Design*

The design of this study was framed within the phenomenological paradigm. From a philosophical perspective, phenomenology is oriented toward understanding lived experience by suspending preconceived judgments that the phenomenon may carry; it allows phenomena to be revealed as they are perceived by those who experience them (Husserl, 2013). Within this research paradigm, the Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) design was adopted, considering it as an approach that seeks to explore how individuals make sense of significant experiences in their lives, with the researcher being aware that such meanings are not fully accessible, but rather are meanings that also require interpretation (Smith & Osborn, 2008; Duque & Aristizábal, 2019). Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis made it possible to understand the meanings attributed to lived experience, which must be experiences that hold particular subjective value for those who have experienced them (Smith & Osborn, 2008; Duque & Aristizábal, 2019).

2.2. *Participants*

The population was defined by the set of all units (people, objects, documents) that share relevant characteristics for the research (Supo, 2014). The population considered for this study consisted of 15 lecturers from a private university in Lima.

2.3. *Measuring instruments*

For this research, the interview technique was a semi-structured interview guide, which integrated themes and open-ended questions designed to encourage participants' expression without imposing external interpretive frameworks. The guide was conceived as a flexible structure that allowed the conversation to be oriented and adapted to the characteristics of each participant's narrative (Smith & Osborn, 2008; Duque & Aristizábal, 2019). In addition, the interviews were conducted in person, after coordinating an appropriate date and time with each participant. Each interview lasted approximately 35 minutes, which fostered in-depth and reflective discussion of the topic under study.

2.4. *Procedure*

The procedure for data analysis A technique is the procedure and specific manner of collecting the data required in a research study (Hernández-Sampieri & Mendoza, 2018). The information collection technique consisted of an interview, as it was the most appropriate for gathering meaningful, nuanced, and situated accounts of the participants' lived experiences (Smith & Osborn, 2008; Duque & Aristizábal, 2019). An instrument is the material means or specific resource used to record the information provided by the units of analysis (Hernández-Sampieri & Mendoza, 2018).

III.RESULTS

Fig. 1 Unit of analysis of pedagogical experiences lived by university teachers

Figure 1 makes it clear that the pedagogical experiences lived by university teachers are articulated through four subcategories that reflect their ways of understanding and practicing didactic transposition, formative guidance, the recovery of knowledge comprehension, and ethical commitment to the student's critical formation. Each subcategory contains themes that reveal meanings, practices, and latent tensions within their teaching practice.

It was observed that, for the university teachers who participated in the study, didactic transposition is established as both a lived and contextualized process. Thus, they do not conceptualize it as a mere technical adjustment of content, but rather understand it as a practice linked to empathy and cognitive justice. The importance attributed to the validation of students' prior knowledge and identity shows that teachers assume students are bearers of their own knowledge, which transforms teaching into a constant conversational process rather than a vertical transmission of information. Likewise, the contextualized transformation of content reveals that disciplinary knowledge is re-signified to adapt to local contexts, individual learning paces, and students' prior knowledge, such that didactic transposition is recognized as an ethical-relational process that goes beyond what is strictly methodological.

Similarly, teaching guidance was considered a contiguous and adaptive experience. For teachers, guidance is a process that requires great patience and closeness, with the intention of avoiding student frustration, which highlights a pedagogy in which emotional education and cognitive education play a relevant role. Joint and flexible planning reinforces this idea, as it shows that the teaching-learning process is shared and allows for continuous variations adapted to each student's characteristics. In this sense, teaching practice reveals a personalized and collaborative approach, in which flexibility becomes a constitutive element that enables meaningful learning.

Likewise, throughout university teaching, the ethical commitment that teachers attribute to their work in relation to students’ critical formation became evident. Ethical rigor and strong responsibility demonstrate that teachers understand their work beyond the mere transmission of content and orient it toward students’ intellectual transformation. This is reflected in the promotion of critical suspicion and the deconstruction of authority, which move away from traditional patterns and invite students to question, analyze, and reconstruct knowledge from an emancipatory stance. Attention to inclusion and epistemic reparation evidences an awareness of inequalities in access to knowledge and a willingness to contribute to their remediation. In sum, these practices express an ethical commitment in teaching oriented toward educational justice and intellectual empowerment.

Finally, university teachers define deep understanding as a transformational experience that goes beyond correct mastery of content. They define deep understanding as a process that reveals the ability to interpret, act, and relate to knowledge in a critical manner. Clarity as an ethic of communication is one of the indispensable conditions for this process, as it understands that comprehension is constructed collaboratively through clear, coherent, and contextualized discourse. Added to this is the empowerment and recovery of the student’s personal voice, indicating that deep understanding fosters autonomy and active participation in one’s own learning. In this pursuit of deep understanding, comprehension is experienced as an emancipatory process that transcends the academic sphere and impacts the student’s identity. These experiences constitute evidence of a humanistic, ethical, and critical teaching practice whose aim is not only the transmission of content, but also the formation of individuals capable of understanding, questioning, and transforming their reality.

Table 1. Teaching practice

Topics	Experienced statements	Quotes
Teaching based on empathy and emotional connection	The teachers agreed that teaching should stem from empathy and emotional connection with students. They recognized that authentic learning arises from understanding students' emotions, concerns, and expectations. Didactic transposition thus becomes a human and reflective act, where the student's feelings help select the relevant content.	“Learning must be born from empathy” (Alberto. 403, p.12). “The selection of content is a profoundly intimate and reflective process where the feelings and experience of the student's context are fundamental pillars” (Wilmer. 5, 6, p.1). “It is about connecting with their emotions, concerns, and expectations” (Wilmer. 10, p.1).
Validation of prior knowledge and identity (cognitive justice)	It was stated that recognizing prior knowledge is an act of cognitive justice and affirmation of identity. For teachers, validating prior knowledge is a process of dignifying learning, as it gives students the feeling that their experience and knowledge are taken into account. The intention is to break down the deeply ingrained stigma surrounding the inability to learn, and to strengthen confidence and personal identity.	Validating prior knowledge is interpreted as cognitive justice” (Arce, 1030, 1031, p. 31). “The first task is to dismantle the myth that they never understood mathematics” (Arce, 1024, 1025, p. 31). “Validating personal experience restores their dignity” (Elmer, 1202, 1203, p. 36). “Learning allows them to strengthen their identity” (Wilmer, 19, p. 1).
Transformation of contextualized content	The teaching experience emphasized that knowledge becomes meaningful in learning when it is contextualized and linked to the student's reality. Including relatable examples transforms learning into a dynamic, meaningful, and critical process that encourages questioning and transforming reality. Theory is redefined as a tool for understanding and acting upon the communicative and social environment.	“By including examples that students recognize, learning is transformed into a living and connected act” (Wilmer. 13, 14, p.1). “Content must cease to be academic topics and become living and meaningful” (Alberto. 490, 491, p.15). “Theory is seen as a tool to name, question, and transform their communicative reality” (Hellen. 749, 750, p.23).

In table 2, the findings of the first theme make it clear that teaching practice is an act grounded in empathy and emotional connection. Empathy as the foundation of teaching is a point on which there is clear convergence among teachers: authentic learning begins with recognizing students’ emotions and expectations. The didactic transposition of knowledge is understood as a sensitive and reflective process. All participants value empathy; moreover, the two interviewees (Alberto and Wilmer) agree on empathy from an ethical standpoint, although they differ in perspective. For Alberto, empathy in teaching is a source of learning; Wilmer translates it into a bridge for connecting with his students’ experiences.

With regard to the validation of prior knowledge and identity, there is convergence in the view that this act gives dignity to learning and strengthens students’ confidence. However, each participant offered a divergent perspective on this assertion: Arce’s reflection focused on the deconstruction of pedagogical myths, Elmer emphasized the ethical dimensions of recognition, and Wilmer highlighted its implications for self-esteem and identity. Although they share the value of recognition, their approaches operate at different levels: pedagogical, ethical, and identity-based.

Regarding the contextualization of content, the shared view among teachers is that knowledge gains meaning when it is connected to students’ reality. That is where learning truly becomes engaging—when it comes to life and ceases to be a mere transmission of information, becoming instead a transformative experience. Of course, each teacher has a distinct style. Wilmer prefers to rely on examples that are familiar to students, whereas Alberto strongly emphasizes experiential learning. Hellen continues to defend the importance of theory. These approaches are not in conflict; rather, they complement one another. All of them pursue the same goal: to give meaning to learning, whether through the practical, the experiential, or the critical. It is precisely within these differences and convergences that a more comprehensive understanding of what it means to teach emerges. Teaching is not only an ethical act; it is also an affective one. At the center of it all is recognizing the student and their context, which is what ultimately makes it possible to build learning experiences that truly matter.

Finally, one of the central contributions of this study is the recognition that the observed practice constitutes a form of sensitive didactic transposition, in which empathy, recognition, and contextualization cease to be mere complements and become essential conditions for meaningful learning. Teachers operate within ethical, affective, and identity-based frameworks that articulate a humanized form of teaching: recognizing the student’s voice, history, and context not only enables learning, but also secures the student’s place within the educational act. The differences among the narratives do not disrupt the continuity of the phenomenon; rather, they offer evidence of its complexity, showing that teaching is a hermeneutic phenomenon in which every pedagogical decision is simultaneously an ethical gesture toward recognition.

Table 2.

Topics	Experienced statements	Quotes
Close and patient support.	The teachers understood their role as one of close, empathetic, and patient support; that is, respecting each student's individual pace. The educators agreed that skills are developed carefully, so they should never be imposed or rushed. This approach, then, creates an	“A close guide who accompanies and paces the process” (Wilmer. 24, 25, p.1). “Skills must be cultivated with care, patience, and a lot of support” (Alberto. 508, 509, 510, p.16). “So that students don’t get lost along the way” (Alberto.

	environment of trust where the student feels safe and understood, thus strengthening the learning relationship.	454, 455, 456, p.14). "They feel supported and confident" (Alberto. 695, 696, p.21).
Progressive structure and avoidance	In the educational process, the planning was designed progressively and based on a programmed logic that could be adapted to each student's pace. In this sense, the teachers agreed that everything should be gradual so as not to impose abstract concepts on the student that might lead them to reject learning or become demotivated. On the contrary, the careful introduction of complexity allows the student to internalize their ability to understand the world and remain motivated to do so, provided it is done consistently and fosters critical thinking grounded in abstraction.	"The organization of content is not linear and rigid, but rather a dynamic, sensitive, and adaptive process" (Wilmer, 64, 65, p. 2). "Complexity is only introduced when a student feels they need a more powerful tool" (Arce, 980, 981, 982, p. 30). "Abstraction should not be a wall, but a bridge" (Arce, 984, p. 30). "Moving forward without a solid foundation leads to frustration and demotivation" (Alberto, 451, 452, p. 14).
Joint and flexible planning	Pedagogical planning is understood as a shared and collaborative process in which teachers and students have equal responsibilities. Those interviewed affirm the need to establish common goals; however, these must be adapted to the realities of the social group. Therefore, flexibility is demonstrated here as a means of achieving equality; that is, if students work, then a way must be found to accommodate their schedules. This premise places at its core the principles of dignity, respect, and autonomy, aimed at providing each student with what they need to progress in their education.	"Joint planning has been described as a space of co-responsibility and authentic dialogue" (Wilmer, 270–273, p. 9). "This flexibility, far from being disorder, creates an environment of trust and collaboration that deepens the research process" (Alberto, 646–648, p. 20). "Complexity is introduced gradually" (Arce, 980–981, p. 30). "Having dignity when conducting research" (Elmer, 1244, p. 37).

Table 2, shows an image of teaching as a deeply human process, full of sensitivity, meticulousness, and constant fluidity. Teachers do not merely retrain students in content; they "walk, listen, and adjust" to their unique paths, understanding that the learning process, as well as learning theory, is not "disembodied," not "deprived" of real bodies and real "times," nor of contexts (Wilmer and Alberto). University teachers converge on a vision of guidance as the provision of close, patient, and committed support, capable of accompanying students at their own unique learning pace. The point of convergence in this aspect is that providing "freedom" as a relationship of "trust" reinforces the fundamental "bond" of pedagogy (Wilmer and Alberto). Divergence appears when Wilmer emphasizes the idea of synchronizing with the student's process, while Alberto's perspective highlights the need to exercise care with both the process and its stages in order to avoid provoking demotivation.

In preventing student frustration, there is an emphasis on the need for teaching to be gradual; that is, progress must match the student's pace (Wilmer and Arce). This way of understanding instruction transforms learning into something tangible rather than rigid. Divergences emerge with Wilmer regarding how to organize content dynamically. Arce suggests introducing complexity only when the student requires it, while Alberto points to the risks of proceeding without a solid foundational starting point.

Regarding joint and flexible planning, university teachers agree that it constitutes a space for dialogue and shared responsibility, which is key to addressing the realities of the group, especially working students (Wilmer, Alberto, and Arce). This type of flexibility is understood as a form of pedagogical justice, insofar as it fosters autonomy and dignity (Elmer).

Finally, the data presented suggest that university teachers hold a deeply human conception of teaching, as it enables them to engage in processes of guidance, care, and trust as means of adapting to students' real learning rhythms. Convergence around freedom, gradualness, and flexibility thus reveals a pedagogy oriented toward connection and care, while points of divergence highlight the different nuances that may exist regarding how learning can be paced or acted upon. At the same time, the relationship among the narratives allows teaching to be conceived as a practice situated within the phenomenon of students' relationship with the educational system, in such a way that frustration is avoided and students are enabled to develop dignified educational trajectories.

IV. DISCUSSION

The results obtained show This chapter analyzes the results concerning the pedagogical experiences of university teachers regarding the didactic transposition of knowledge and research skills. The aim is to interpret the results based on the theoretical framework and then compare the study's findings with previous research. The discussion follows the specific objectives of the study and is organized into four central subcategories: didactic transposition and the contextualization of knowledge; guidance and adaptation to each student's pace; the value of recovering deep understanding in student transformation; and ethical commitment to critical education and the safeguarding of knowledge.

With regard to didactic transposition and contextualized knowledge, it is made clear that university teachers view transposition as a process of re-signifying disciplinary knowledge. It is not merely about modifying content so that students can understand it; rather, it involves doing so from an empathetic, equitable, and situated perspective. University teachers do not simply translate information; they connect it with students' worlds and emotions. In this way, teaching becomes a much more human endeavor. This expands Chevallard's (1985) conception of transposition as the shift from scholarly knowledge to teachable knowledge, as ethical and affective dimensions now come into play as essential elements for meaningful learning.

When compared with other studies, the results align with López-Gutiérrez and Pérez (2021), who indicate that this didactic process impacts key aspects such as motivation, pedagogical goals, and classroom communication. In this study, teachers clearly understand that teaching is not merely about transmitting information; it involves creating connections and re-signifying content based on each student's experience. This resonates with Zapata et al. (2022), who argue that didactic transposition should be plural and situated, valuing community knowledge within the educational process.

At the same time, there are discrepancies with studies such as Roa and Hidalgo-Herrero (2022), who warn that applying didactic transposition in highly traditional contexts may risk oversimplifying content. However, the teachers in this study view contextualization as an opportunity to deepen learning by linking theory with real problems faced by students. This difference is related to the phenomenological approach used in this research, which allowed exploration of teaching experience from within, avoiding generalizations that obscure contextual richness.

The way teachers in this study understand didactic transposition goes beyond merely adjusting the curriculum. It involves making teaching an ethical act that engages emotions and acknowledges cultures. This fundamentally transforms the role of the university teacher, who is no longer simply a transmitter of knowledge, but someone who bridges scientific knowledge with students' everyday lives. Teaching thus becomes a space where theory and lived experience intersect, making education more approachable, fair, and authentic.

Regarding guidance and adaptation to each student's pace, the data show that teachers view teaching as a process requiring patience, gradual accompaniment, and respect for individual differences. This pedagogical perspective is grounded in the belief that recognizing individual learning rhythms constitutes a genuine form of educational equity. This aligns with Vygotsky's (1978) theory that learning is constructed through guided mediation, particularly within the zone of proximal development, where teachers support and facilitate cognitive processes.

Díaz (2005) emphasizes that pedagogical mediation is essential for students to truly appropriate knowledge, a principle strongly reflected in the teaching practices analyzed in this study. University teachers do not perceive guidance as surveillance, but as shared responsibility, where students actively participate in planning, monitoring, and evaluating their own learning. This approach is consistent with Jaime et al. (2021), who advocate transforming the university by placing students at the center through participatory methods.

However, an interesting divergence arises with Navarrete and Cerón (2022), who emphasize co-teaching and collaborative work among teachers as the foundation of didactic transposition. In contrast, the teachers in this study place special emphasis on direct and personalized relationships with students. This difference can be attributed to institutional structures and the methodological approach employed, which centers on individual experiences in university classrooms. Consequently, the university teacher becomes a distinctive personal guide throughout the learning process.

From this perspective, aligning with each student's pace is not merely a strategy, but an inclusive practice that fosters independence, confidence, and research skills. This aligns with Tobón's (2010) competency-based education framework, which emphasizes that competencies are cultivated gradually through the integration of theory, practice, and reflection. Teaching flexibility thus emerges as both an ethical principle and a methodological approach that ensures equity and relevance in higher education.

Regarding deep understanding and critical student transformation, the findings reveal that teachers believe students can reinterpret and reconstruct knowledge through their own experiences, moving beyond rote memorization. This aligns with Perrenoud's (1993) view that formative assessment should activate knowledge in real situations to make learning meaningful. It also resonates with Reyes-Rodríguez and Concepción-Pérez (2022), who argue that developing research skills requires reflection and critical thinking rather than purely technical training. Interviewed teachers assume that genuine learning occurs when students use knowledge to critically analyze and intervene in their environment.

This perspective is consistent with Torres et al. (2021), who present didactic transposition as a means of fostering contextualized and transformative teaching, particularly in technical and communicative fields. However, this study goes further by incorporating ethical and emotional dimensions as essential components of deep understanding. Here, knowledge is not only applied, but also lived and felt.

Recovering the student's voice is not merely a matter of self-esteem; it represents a crucial step toward intellectual empowerment. This personal dimension aligns with Gutiérrez et al. (2022), who argue that language and grammar instruction is ineffective when motivation and identity are excluded. In this study, students' autonomous expression is seen as a sign of cognitive and emotional maturity, grounded in lived experience rather than rigid frameworks.

Divergences with prior studies appear in the strong emphasis placed on ethical communication. While other approaches prioritize cognitive aspects, the teachers interviewed here view conceptual clarity and argumentative coherence as reflections of intellectual integrity and respect for others. For them, honesty in the use of knowledge matters deeply. Thus, education is conceived as an integral practice: critical transformation extends beyond cognition to ethical formation and social commitment.

Regarding ethical commitment to critical education and the safeguarding of knowledge, a clear idea emerges: university teaching is not merely a job, but a profoundly ethical practice with social and epistemological implications. Teachers view knowledge as a collective good that must be protected, critically examined, and transmitted with honesty. This perspective aligns with Chevallard (1985) and with the reflections shared by Elmer in his interview, emphasizing methodological coherence in transforming knowledge for teaching. It also converges with Rueda et al. (2022), who argue that strengthening research skills begins with intellectual honesty and transparency.

In response to biased content and misinformation, university teachers adopt an active stance, encouraging students to read sources critically, analyze information, and reflect. This approach, highlighted by Hellen and supported by Reyes-Rodríguez and Concepción-Pérez (2022), positions the teacher as a facilitator of critical thinking and a defender of intellectual autonomy. Zapata et al. (2022) similarly argue that incorporating local or community knowledge is not an additive gesture, but a means of repairing historical epistemic exclusion. Teachers who bring these voices into their teaching do so not symbolically, but as an act of cognitive justice, recognizing that knowledge originates from diverse sources and perspectives.

There are, however, discrepancies with authors such as Roa and Hidalgo-Herrero (2022), who emphasize academic rigor in terms of technical precision and formal structure. The teachers in this study move beyond this view, understanding rigor as closely tied to an ethic of recognition. Caring for citations, contextualizing content, and validating sources are acts of respect toward others and toward science itself. This perspective aligns with the phenomenological paradigm adopted here, which prioritizes how educational actors experience and give meaning to their practice rather than focusing solely on empirical verification. Teachers see themselves as guardians of knowledge, assuming this role ethically, critically, and inclusively. For them, safeguarding knowledge is not merely about technical quality, but about actively defending the right to learn and to be recognized as epistemic subjects. Analytical instruction thus becomes a liberating practice that questions presumed objectivity and embraces cognitive justice.

The interpretation of results is grounded in the Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) design, which allows for in-depth exploration of university teachers' lived pedagogical experiences. Following Smith and Osborn (2008) and Duque and Aristizábal (2019), the study emphasizes the meanings teachers themselves attribute to their work, recognizing each experience as unique and shaped by context and personal identity. This methodological choice responds to the need to capture lived realities without reducing them to simplistic explanations, preserving contextual richness.

Furthermore, the findings demonstrate that university teaching grounded in didactic transposition and the development of research competencies goes far beyond instrumental instruction. It becomes an ethically, humanly, and transformatively significant educational experience. Convergences with the reviewed literature confirm that the contemporary role of the university teacher is no longer limited to information transmission, but includes mediating knowledge, facilitating cognitive processes, and creating meaningful learning experiences. Divergences can be explained by methodological characteristics of the phenomenological approach and by contextual conditions of the Peruvian higher education system. Thus, teaching practice in higher education requires profound epistemological and ethical reconfiguration. Didactic transposition is not merely a curricular adaptation technique; it is a conscious pedagogical action that recognizes student diversity, promotes critical thinking, and fosters integral education.

This discussion shows that didactic transposition, guidance, deep understanding, and ethical safeguarding of knowledge do not function as isolated subcategories, but as an interconnected pedagogical framework that gives meaning to the university educational experience. From a phenomenological-interpretative perspective, teachers do not merely apply strategies; they construct ethical, affective, and critical meanings that guide their teaching. The findings indicate that teaching practice is oriented toward an integral model that transcends technicality and promotes contextualized knowledge, respect for individual rhythms, critical reflection, and cognitive justice. The divergences identified reflect the diversity of interpretations and contexts that enrich the phenomenon, confirming that didactic transposition, when lived through teaching experience, becomes an ethical and situated practice that not only transmits content, but also forms critical subjects capable of understanding, transforming, and inhabiting knowledge consciously and justly.

Finally, this study was subject to certain limitations inherent to a qualitative approach. The sample size was small, consisting of only five teacher informants. Nevertheless, as established in Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (Smith & Osborn, 2008; Duque & Aristizábal, 2019), this number is appropriate, as a range of three to ten participants allows for in-depth exploration of experiences. Thus, the results provide a rich and contextualized interpretation of the phenomena studied. Additionally, the information collected depended largely on the participants' attitudes and openness during interviews, which may have influenced the depth and accuracy of their accounts. Limited time for data collection and analysis also restricted prolonged observation or triangulation through other methods such as focus groups or institutional document analysis. Furthermore, the institution showed some resistance to providing complementary information regarding its research training policies, limiting opportunities for institutional comparison. Finally, since the phenomenon under analysis is closely linked to subjective and situational factors, the interpretation of meanings may have been influenced by the theoretical frameworks employed and by the researcher's own experience.

V. CONCLUSIONS

According to the general objective, it was concluded that transposition and research skills went beyond the mere transmission of knowledge, establishing themselves as a complex and reflective process grounded in ethical principles. In this sense, the teacher emerged as a mediator and guide of learning, reconstructing and contextualizing knowledge in accordance with the student's comprehensive education. Didactic transposition became a dialectical practice, understood as the reinterpretation and adaptation of academic content to the sociocultural and cognitive reality of the student. This practice was grounded in principles of pedagogical empathy, cognitive justice, meaningful understanding, and ethical commitment; these principles made it possible to establish a form of teaching that is critical, humanizing, and socially relevant.

Likewise, with regard to Specific Objective 1, university-level faculty demonstrated improvements in efforts related to the selection and organization of content for contextualized knowledge, showing a preference for content connected to the student's own sociocultural context. However, the limited practical use of systematic content organization based on clearly defined criteria—aimed at achieving effective searching for reliable information and its analysis—restricted the potential for the autonomous development of research competencies.

Similarly, in relation to Specific Objective 2, pedagogical experiences of accompaniment and adaptation to the student's learning pace were linked to the adjustment of knowledge and the search for relevant information. These experiences revealed efforts by university faculty to relate and adapt academic content to the student's reality; however, the predominance of traditional methodologies hindered the production of critical learning, causing research-related knowledge to be appropriated in a less meaningful manner.

Furthermore, regarding Specific Objective 3, from the perspective of university faculty as protagonists of deep understanding, this process proved fundamental in the student's critical transformation. Nevertheless, the types of assessment strategies employed tended to emphasize memorization and reproduction rather than reflection, critical analysis, knowledge construction, and the consolidation of new models of knowledge. This situation highlighted a space in which research didactics require a clear formative and reflective orientation.

Finally, in relation to Specific Objective 4, the ethical commitment to the monitoring of knowledge in research was positioned at a declarative level (more theoretical than practical). This form of training requires greater systematicity—understood as an ordered, continuous, and structured process—since it has not been adequately implemented in a transversal manner across academic activities or courses. This limitation constrained the development of a reflective, critical, and responsible educational culture.

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